

How to Support Preprint Sharing

Six Levers to Advance Equitable Research Access

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Executive Summary

The current research publishing system is failing science and society. It drains resources through the vast sums spent on Article Processing Charges (APCs); it entrenches inequalities in who can publish; and it limits access to evidence through access restrictions and publication delays. The prioritisation of prestige publication over research quality has created perverse research incentives and demands systemic reform.

Preprints, research articles uploaded to a public server before peer review, offer a practical path forward. They enable the earliest possible access to evidence and remove cost barriers providing an equitable alternative to pay-to-publish models. Yet only 4–6% of scholarly publications are currently shared as preprints.

Preprint sharing is uneven across disciplines and regions, with preprints well-established in mathematics and physics but more limited in social sciences and arts and humanities. Researchers, particularly early-career and Global South scholars, face real risks: as preprints are not yet widely recognised in research assessment, career progression, or grant applications. There are also challenges with commercial capture of preprint infrastructure and how best to integrate preprint sharing with peer review and journal publication.

This policy paper's starting point is that sharing preprints is a good thing for the scientific communication system and advancing evidence access. We identify six levers to drive change drawn from an evidence review and expert interviews. Each lever is accompanied by policy pointers and real-world spotlights.

Six Levers for Research Funders and Policymakers

1

National STI Policies — prioritise Open Science principles in national STI frameworks including equitable Open Access publication, transparent peer review and recognition of diverse outputs, including preprints.

2

Preprint Policies — establish standalone or integrated preprint policies that confirm preprints as a valid route to Open Access compliance and provide researchers with guidance on preprint sharing.

3

Research Assessment — recognise preprints in grant applications, reporting, and review processes; train committees to value early sharing over publication venue.

4

Awareness & Capacity — invest in training and embed preprint guidance within researcher support programmes, back existing capacity and awareness raising initiatives.

5

Preprint Infrastructure — fund community-led, open preprint servers and related tools to ensure sustainability and guard against commercial capture.

6

Collective Action & Science Diplomacy — work through coalitions, multilateral agreements, and bilateral partnerships to create shared incentive frameworks that recognise and reward preprint sharing internationally.

Call to action

No single funder or government can shift global publication norms alone. Collective action through Open Science coalitions, reforms to research assessment, targeted investment in infrastructure, and science diplomacy is essential. Research funders should adopt or update preprint policies, recognise preprints in research assessment frameworks, and invest in equitable, community-owned preprint infrastructure. Policymakers should embed Open Science commitments in national STI strategies and champion preprints and Open Science in bilateral and multilateral dialogue. Together, these six levers can support preprint sharing and equitable research access.

Acronyms

APC — Article Processing Charge
 AREN — Africa Reproducibility Network
 BBSRC — Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council
 CoARA — Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
 DORA — San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
 ISC — International Science Council
 MRC — Medical Research Council
 NREN — National Research and Education Network
 SciELO — Scientific Electronic Library Online
 STI — Science, Technology and Innovation
 UNESCO — United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
 WACREN — West and Central African Research and Education Network

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Introduction

The current research publishing system is not working for science, researchers, or society. The system drains the academic community of money, time, trust, and control and limits access to research outside of academia (Beigel et al., 2025). Reforms to research publishing need to consider the purpose of research articles and how a research communication system can be built that better serves science and society.

Research articles are vital mechanism for sharing evidence, but the current prestige publication system leads to long publication delays and overvalues the venue of publication over the intrinsic quality or relevance of the research.

The shift to Open Access has enhanced research accessibility for readers, but because of the pivot by many publishers to pay-to-publish models that level Article Processing Charges (APCs) inequalities in who can publish Open Access have been entrenched. This publication model is costing research funders significant sums of money to achieve Open Access, with estimates of between \$74 million and \$81 million spent on APCs in 2023 by just 21 research funders (Chadwick El-Ali et al., 2025).

Preprints, research articles published before journal peer review, offer a practical step towards system reform. They enable the earliest possible access to research evidence, with the potential to improve science and speed up discovery, innovation and impact. Preprints could also be an equitable alternative to pay-to-publish Open Access models: as researchers can share their work openly with no cost. For researchers, especially early career and Global South scholars, preprints also provide a way to evidence their contributions without waiting for lengthy journal publication timelines.

What is a preprint?

A preprint is a research article that is uploaded to a public server for everyone to read and reuse (license depending) ahead of peer review or publication in an academic journal. In some disciplines e.g., economics they are called working papers.

Preprint servers usually conduct initial quality-control measures before uploading, and most support versioning, posting updated versions of the paper based on feedback, peer review and/or new data. Many servers have integrated comment and review functions. (Adapted from ASAPbio n.d. and Penfold, 2022).

Sharing preprints is not yet mainstream academic practice. Estimates suggest only 4-6% of academic articles are currently posted as preprints (Drury, 2022; Rzayeva et al., 2026). There are disciplinary differences: in physics, preprints have been a normal part of research communication practice for decades, whilst preprint sharing has gained traction in the life sciences in recent years (Coates, 2026). The COVID-19 pandemic saw a rapid increase in preprint sharing through funder-imposed mandates and researcher commitments to sharing knowledge to address the public health emergency (Fraser et al., 2021).

Preprint sharing could save research funders, institutions and researchers time and money, overcoming publication delays, removing cost barriers to dissemination, and enhancing the visibility of research. However, there are still obstacles to preprint sharing becoming normal research practice, including recognition of preprints within research assessment processes and a lack of alternative signals of publication integrity beyond journal peer review. The lack of recognition of preprint sharing means it can still feel risky to individual researchers to publish this way, especially those who are already relatively disadvantaged or struggling for visibility and recognition in the current research system.

Preprint sharing intersects with other Open Science practices such as Open Data and transparent peer review. For research funders support for preprint sharing is part of a strategic prioritisation of Open Science across a funder's investments, funding strategy and grant policies. Research funders with strategic commitments to Open Science and research publishing reform to better serve science and society are increasingly recommending and, in some instances mandating preprint sharing for their grantees (e.g., Gates Foundation, Howard Hughes Medical Institute). For STI adjacent policymakers and research funders committed to Open Science incentivising preprint sharing is one of the most tractable interventions available to shift publication norms.

This policy paper's starting point is that sharing preprints is a good thing for the scientific communication system and for evidence access. Drawing on a review of existing evidence and expert interviews (see Annex: Approach to policy paper development), this paper identifies six levers through which research funders and policymakers can accelerate preprint adoption. Each lever is accompanied by policy pointers and real-world spotlights.

Background: preprint sharing

Understanding the challenges with preprint adoption and where the tensions lie is essential context for research funders and policymakers to understand how they can support adoption. There are five key issues: researcher awareness and perspectives on preprint sharing; the extent to which preprints are integrated within the existing publishing system; preprints, publishing integrity and peer review; infrastructure to enable preprint sharing; and recognition of preprints in research assessment processes.

Researcher awareness and perspectives on preprint sharing

Adoption of preprints varies across scientific disciplines and geographies. The physical sciences, especially physics, astronomy, mathematics and computer science lead the way (Ni & Waltman, 2024). For mathematics, 27% of journal articles can be linked to a preprint in 2022 and 20% for physics (Rzayeva et al., 2026). There was an increase in sharing preprints in the life and medical sciences from 2020, likely bolstered by the demand for timely evidence during the COVID-19 pandemic. In other disciplines sharing preprints is not as common, the social sciences and the arts and humanities are much less familiar with preprint sharing (Ni & Waltman, 2024), although there has been a modest rise in preprint sharing in economics in recent years (Rzayeva et al., 2026).

There are also regional differences in familiarity and adoption of preprint sharing. Awareness is highest in the United States and Europe, and lower in China, East Asia, Middle East and North Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean (Ni & Waltman, 2024). Western Europe has the highest adoption of preprints with 13% of journal articles being linked to a preprint in 2022. Other regions hover around the global average of 4-6% - with Latin America and the Caribbean and East Asia at 6% in 2022 (Rzayeva et al., 2026). A small regional study in Africa found 42% of respondents had posted a preprint at some point in their career. This study found that African researchers mostly post preprints as part of the journal publishing process rather than ahead of journal publication (David et al., 2024).

Benefits of preprint sharing

- Increases discoverability of research
- Enables feedback and review from a wider audience
- Establishes priority of work
- Enables researchers to evidence their work outside of long journal publication timelines

(Otto et al., 2024)

Although some of these disciplinary and geographic differences are explained by limited awareness or disciplinary norms, there are also concerns with preprint sharing amongst parts of the research community. Some early career researchers have fears, even if unfounded, of research being scooped or may be unwilling to share work that has not been validated through peer reviewed (Chadwick El-Ali et al., 2025). Additionally, the lack of recognition of preprint sharing by research funders and institutions means it can still feel risky to individual researchers to publish this way, especially those who are already disadvantaged or who need to gain recognition within the prestige publication system for career advancement or funding.

Journal and preprint integration

There are different views on the future of preprints within the research communication system, and the extent to which preprints integrate with existing journal publishing infrastructure. Some preprint advocates see the potential for preprints to replace the need for journal articles entirely (Irfanullah, 2025), whilst others see preprints as the first stage of a more transparent research communication system, with journal services overlaid on top (Chtena et al., 2025). The integration of preprints within existing journal publication processes, realises the benefits of preprint sharing in the form of transparency and timely sharing, whilst lowering risks for researchers who are still able to publish in academic journals (Penfold, 2022). For example, SciELO's preprint server is the starting point for the publication workflow, researchers submit their article as a preprint involving preliminary integrity checks, and from there the article can be submitted to SciELO-hosted journals and undergo peer review ahead of publication. The original preprint version is maintained as part of the scholarly record, enhancing transparency.

The integration of preprints into the journal system necessitates journals accepting preprint sharing ahead of article publication. Some journals do not accept articles that have already been shared as preprints (e.g., Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science). However, numerous commercial and not-for-profit/society publishers strongly support preprint sharing (e.g., Taylor and Francis and Wiley). Some publishers proactively approach authors who have uploaded manuscripts on preprint servers (e.g., Portland Press). Others have their own preprint community (e.g., Wiley "Authorea"). There are examples of collaboration between journals and preprint servers to support integration of preprints into existing publication mechanisms. The Royal Society's Open Biology, Royal Society Open Science, Biology Letters, Proceedings B and Journal of the Royal Society Interface support submission of manuscripts directly from the bioRxiv, allowing authors to transfer their article information and metadata without re-uploading the files.

Although integration between preprint servers and the commercial publishing sector could ensure sustainability of preprint infrastructure (Puebla et al., 2022), this integration could also adversely impact scholarly control of preprint sharing. The increasingly dominant role commercial publishers are playing in the preprint server space needs to be considered carefully. Research Square is owned by Springer Nature and SSRN was independent but has since been bought by Elsevier. This indicates future commercial pivots to accommodate and commercialise Open Science practices, including potentially using preprint servers to act as feeders to Open Access journals levying APCs.

Preprints, publishing integrity and peer review

Peer review is considered by many as the core trust signal for the integrity of research articles. The lack of initial peer review of preprints remains a barrier to increased adoption with concerns about the lack of quality assurance of preprints (Blatch-Jones et al., 2023). However, concerns with the lack of peer review of preprints needs to be situated in the context of significant problems with the traditional journal-based peer-review system. The rapid increase in research outputs has put the system under strain adding to publication delays, and the drain on researchers' time (Horta & Jung, 2024). There is a broader publishing integrity challenge, amplified by generative AI and paper mills, and prominent examples of research fraud or malpractice not being detected through journal peer-review mechanisms (Harington, 2022).

Although there is preliminary evidence showing that Open Science behaviours (such as sharing preprints) might function as trust signals indicating a researcher's openness to expose their work to public scrutiny (Vines et al., 2026). Currently, efforts are prioritising integrating review services with preprint sharing through several existing models.

- Publish, Review, Curate: a journal publication model in which a preprint is first shared, then reviewed publicly before an updated version of the article is shared addressing the review feedback. The platform preserves the preprint, peer review comments and updated final article – enhancing transparency (e.g., [F1000 publishing platforms](#) as currently used by Open Research Africa and Gates Open Research).
- Independent and community-led review platforms: these services are separate from journals and often overlay or are integrated onto preprint servers. Some of these services allow researchers to request or receive open feedback on their preprints. Examples include: [PREreview](#), [Review Commons](#) and [Peer Community in](#).
- Other publisher review services: publisher platforms or services for providing preprint review. A prominent example is [eLife's reviewed preprints model](#), where the conventional accept/reject approach is not used, rather all preprints are published alongside peer review comments and editorial assessments.

Despite increased promotion and capacity strengthening efforts in support of preprint review, studies show that very few preprints receive comments, and if they do, their depth is inadequate (with a median length of comment of 43 words) (Carneiro et al., 2023). A study by Henriques et al. (2025) suggests that scholarly communications are moving towards a mixed approach in which preprint servers, preprint review services, and journals complement each other. Given that most preprint review services are currently seen as a complement or supplement to journal-based review systems, there are questions as to whether currently preprints can offer a radical alternative to journal based articles, or whether they are more likely to become the first stage of research dissemination within a more transparent journal publication system.

Preprint infrastructure

The infrastructure that enables preprint sharing includes both servers and additional products, services and tools that support article metadata, indexing, translation, curation, review and annotation and long-term preservation (Penfold, 2022b). Preprint servers have grown in recent year with over 40 being established in the last decade (Drury, 2022).

There are many region or discipline specific servers. ASAPBio hosts a [directory of preprint servers on their website](#).

The current infrastructure for preprint sharing is not all community-owned or open. As indicated in the section on preprints and journal integration, commercial publishers are significant players in the preprint server space. Beyond risks of commercial control, there are concerns with both the structural and financial sustainability of existing infrastructure. Structurally, concerns with how preprint servers integrate with new publishing workflows especially when built on older proprietary platforms, and their capacity to support growth in preprint sharing. Permanence and back up of existing preprint servers is also an issue, infrastructure needs updating and modernising to allow for other services to plug in and layer on top, such as preprint peer review. Financially, open infrastructure is not free to run. Most community-owned preprint servers are run through institutional in-kind support and philanthropic grants. Plans need to be developed to ensure the sustainability of community-owned preprint infrastructure. If commercial entities continue to play a role in sustaining preprint servers, as seems likely, safeguards may need to be in place to sustain scholarly control.

Recognition in research assessment

A core challenge with preprint adoption is the lack of recognition of preprints within research assessment by research funders and institutions. Whilst research assessment and career progression incentives are built on prestige publication rather than transparency and early sharing, researcher behaviour is unlikely to change beyond those disciplines with an existing disciplinary norm of preprint sharing, e.g., physics, or researchers with a personal commitment to Open Science practices. This is especially true for researchers and institutions in the Global South, who have been excluded from Global scholarship, and are reliant on journal credibility to secure international visibility, positions, and funding.

The recognition of preprints as a research output for research assessment by institutions and funders is a crucial change needed to incentivise preprint sharing. Existing guidance suggests that research institutions need to recognise preprints in graduation and hiring and promotion processes, and that research funders need to recognise preprints when assessing grant proposals and in grant reporting (Otto et al., 2024).

In some countries, national regulatory or institutional research assessment frameworks constrain the shift towards preprints, by indicating lists of journals that researchers must publish in for career progression. Prior to 2024, India's University Grants Commission maintained an approved journal list for academic promotion (Packer, 2025). In South Africa, researchers and their institutions are incentivised by subsidies for publication in prestige journals. Although journal publication does not usually prevent preprint sharing, the focus on journal publication as the indicator of research success disincentivises early sharing via a preprint. Where such structural barriers to change exist at the national level, there is a direct role for policymakers in driving reform.

Review of research funder positions on preprints

INASP's review of Open Access policy options for research funders identified preprints as a critical and underutilised mechanism for ensuring early access to research evidence (Chadwick El-Ali et al., 2025). However, for this benefit to be realised and preprints to be an achievable and equitable route to Open Access, funders and institutions need to align their policies and research assessment frameworks to support preprint sharing.

We reviewed the Open Access policies of 21 research funders with a global development focus or portfolio and found that only seven funders currently address preprints as part of their Open Access policy (see [Table 1](#)). Only one of these funders mandates preprint sharing – Gates Foundation – whilst four funders encourage or strongly recommend sharing preprints. Four funders explicitly state that preprint sharing is a route to Open Access compliance [1].

Incentivising preprint sharing also requires changes to research assessment and recognition of diverse outputs including preprints. It is harder to ascertain research funder positions on recognition of preprints in research assessment. Information indicating acceptance of preprints in review of grant applications and reporting was readily available for five of the research funders in our sample (Gates Foundation, National Institute of Health Research, Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research, UK Research and Innovation, and Wellcome Trust). Increased visibility of acceptance of preprints in research assessment is important, especially given funders public support for research assessment reform efforts such as the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#) and the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) – see Table 1.

[1] Funder policies were assessed in January and February 2026, there may have been subsequent changes in funder policy regarding preprints.

Table 1. Research funder support for research assessment reform and preprint positions within Open Access policies

Funder	Support for research assessment reform initiatives (e.g., DORA, CoARA)*	Position on preprints in research assessment**	Position on preprints in Open Access policy
Agence Française de Développement			
Arcadia Fund	Yes		
Austrian Science Fund	Yes		
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	Yes		Preprint sharing route to Open Access compliance
Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office			Preprints encouraged can be mandated when significant humanitarian need – route to Open Access compliance
Gates Foundation	Yes	Allowed in all reporting	Preprints mandated with exceptions route to Open Access compliance
Horizon Europe	Yes		
International Development Research Centre	Yes, via Research Quality+ Framework		
Japan Science and Technology Agency			Preprint sharing route to Open Access compliance
National Institute of Health Research		Allowed in all reporting	States not in Open Access policy scope
National Institutes of Health			States not in Open Access policy scope
Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research	Yes	Allowed in some reporting	
Research Council of Norway	Yes		
Swedish Research Council	Yes		
Swiss National Science Foundation	Yes		
Templeton World Charity Foundation	Yes		Preprints encouraged
The Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation			
UK Research and Innovation	Yes	MRC and BBSRC state allowed in all reporting	Preprints encouraged
Wellcome Trust	Yes	Allowed in all reporting	Preprints encouraged can be mandated when significant humanitarian need
World Bank			
World Health Organisation			

* Yes, indicates public evidence of support for research assessment reform initiatives and activities

** We only accessed easily searchable information on recognition of preprints in grant award and reporting. Other funders in this list may accept preprints but the information was not easily accessible.

Dark green indicates the strongest support for research assessment reform and preprint positions, light green indicates good support for preprint sharing, yellow is neutral on preprint sharing and blank is where there was no available information.

Six levers to support preprint sharing

Lever 1: National STI policies and Open Science commitments

National STI policies and strategies set the direction for public research investment and signal priorities to funders, institutions, and international partners. A national commitment to Open Science, including recognition of diverse research outputs and equitable access to findings, creates the enabling conditions for preprint adoption. This can drive actions and investments and facilitate international collaboration in support of Open Science.

This does not necessarily require a preprint-specific policy although in some instances that could be helpful; rather it means embedding Open Science principles in existing STI frameworks in ways that reward early access, transparency and research quality over publication prestige.

Spotlight: Uganda National Open Science Policy

The [Ugandan National Open Science Policy](#) has several commitments that if translated into policy by research funding agencies and research institutions would incentivise preprint sharing:

- Commitment to responsible research and researcher evaluation and assessment — focusing on quality of science and recognising diversity of research outputs beyond journal articles e.g., preprints.
- Commitment to open access and transparency around peer review — supported by models such as publish, review, curate.

These commitments can help support the incentive structure to enable wider preprint sharing amongst researchers by ensuring researchers are rewarded for preprint sharing, and moving to transparent peer-review models, which necessitate preprint sharing.

Lever 2: Preprint policies

Preprint sharing supports the earliest possible access to research evidence a fundamental principle of the Open Access movement. Research funder policies, whether preprint specific or part of an Open Access policy, play an important role in signalling support for preprint sharing by indicating the legitimacy and acceptability of preprints as a research output and shaping research norms amongst researchers and institutions.

Research funder policies should indicate a clear position on preprints, including whether preprint sharing is a compliant route to Open Access. For funders spending significant sums on APCs or facing resource-barriers to covering publication costs redirecting support towards preprint-first approaches offers substantial value for money, ensuring research funds support doing research rather than research publication. ASAPbio and Creative Commons have created a [Preprint Policy Framework](#) to support research funders with developing policy text on preprints (see Table 2 below). They have also reviewed a sample of funders existing policies on preprints against this framework.

Table 2. ASAPbio and Creative Commons Preprint Policy Framework

Preprint Requirement	Preprints are either required or strongly recommended to be submitted to a publicly accessible server that issues a Persistent Identifier (such as a DOI) and made available at no cost to the author (to post) nor to the reader (to view).
Author's Copyright	Authors retain copyright of their preprint (unless waived through a CC0 public domain dedication or other arrangements like U.S. government work).
CC BY Licensing	A CC BY license is required or strongly recommended for preprints (unless waived through a CC0 public domain dedication).
Submission Timeline	Preprints are uploaded to a server before or by the time of submission to a peer-reviewed outlet.
Funder Acknowledgement	Institutional affiliations, funders, and/or grants are acknowledged in the preprint's acknowledgments and/or its metadata.
Availability Statement	A key resource table and/or availability statement is required or strongly recommended – outlining where the associated data, code, software, protocols, and key materials can be accessed or are deposited (with the appropriate persistent identifiers, if available).

Reproduced from (ASAPbio, 2025)

Spotlight: Gates Foundation preprint policy

The Gates Foundation first launched an Open Access policy in 2015. [The 2025 policy update](#) aims to deprioritise the importance of the venue of publication and prioritise immediate sharing of findings by mandating the sharing of preprints by all grantees, Gates now no longer funds APCs. This approach aims to shift towards a publishing system where authors can share their work openly and quickly without incurring costs. This has allowed the foundation to reinvest money that would have been spent on APCs into more equitable publishing infrastructure and innovations. The policy has led many researchers to preprint for the first time but has also shown how entrenched prestige publication is within current academic career incentives — highlighting the need for broader sector-wide reform.

Lever 3: Research assessment policies and frameworks

Reforms to research assessment by institutions and funders are vital to create a framework that incentivises preprint sharing. Preprint adoption will only become mainstream when research assessment frameworks at the funder, institutional, and national level explicitly recognise preprints as legitimate research outputs.

Change requires deliberate action: funders must recognise preprints in grant applications and reporting, train review committees to value them, and support institutional and policy reform where national regulations create barriers.

Spotlight: Wellcome Trust recognising preprints in grant applications

The Wellcome Trust recognises preprints in grant applications. This shift aims to support early-career researchers, allowing them to evidence their contributions without being restricted by journal publication timelines. It also forms part of Wellcome's commitment to assessing research quality rather than publication venue through its support for [DORA](#) and commitment to [CoARA](#).

Lever 4: Awareness and capacity strengthening

Policy change must be accompanied by awareness-building. Low researcher awareness and knowledge remains a key barrier to preprint adoption — reinforced by the dominance of prestige publication norms. It can still feel risky to individual researchers to publish preprints, especially those who are already relatively disadvantaged or struggling for visibility and recognition in the current system.

There is a role for policymakers in ensuring Open Science is prioritised in national STI education frameworks. Funders also play an important role, they should embed preprint training and guidance in grantee support and researcher development programmes, this could be part of a broader Open Science curriculum or linked to research dissemination policies. Funders should also support existing researcher-led capacity-strengthening initiatives to ensure they reach different parts of the research community.

Spotlight: AREN capacity strengthening for Open Science

[The Africa Reproducibility Network \(AREN\)](#) provides training and capacity strengthening for researchers on Open Science practices including preprints. They also advocate and build awareness amongst the broader research ecosystem in Africa highlighting the value of Open Science. At the researcher level they focus on early career researchers seeing the behaviour of more experienced researchers as harder to shift.

Spotlight: PREreview support for preprint review

PREreview aims to support equity and transparency in peer review by engaging researchers at the early stages of their career and those historically excluded to openly review preprints. They provide a platform to review preprints and, recently, datasets, as well as training and development activities for researchers. They offer virtual and in-person sessions called 'PREreview Open Reviewers Workshops'. The 2-hour workshops focus on the basics of open and preprint peer review, while 4 to 6-hour sessions include collaborative live review calls facilitated by PREreview staff in which researchers come together to review a preprint.

Lever 5: Support for preprint infrastructure

There are concerns with the structural and financial sustainability of current preprint infrastructure. Open infrastructure is not free to run, many community-run servers need investment to support integration with publishing workflows, permanence and back-up and an increase in users.

Long-term financing mechanisms need to be developed to support this vital infrastructure and ensure that it is available to researchers wherever they are based. There are risks with commercial capture or buy-out of existing infrastructure, which could lead to a loss of scholarly control and Open Science principles.

Maintaining a diversity of preprint servers is important as it gives choices — at regional versus global level as well as providing discipline specific solutions. Diversity will ensure better discoverability if there is interoperability of systems and consistent recording of metadata.

Spotlight: Invest in Open Infrastructure funding coordination

Invest in Open Infrastructure acts as a coordination mechanism to fund the Open Science infrastructure that science relies upon. It provides data and research to help funders and research institutions make informed investments in the infrastructure that their communities need. It produces an annual state of Open Infrastructure report and provides an opportunity to invest in innovative funding models through funding pilots. One of the infrastructures it supports is the Open Preprints System, open-source software for building a preprint server developed by the Public Knowledge Project in Canada. This software supports scholarly led and open preprint servers rather than commercial proprietary solutions.

Spotlight: LIBSENSE African Open Science infrastructure

LIBSENSE (Library Support for Embedded NREN (National Research and Education Network) Services and E-infrastructure) is a pan-African effort to build a community of practice for Open Science initiated by the West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN). LIBSENSE supports the adoption of Open Science policies and the development of supportive services and infrastructure. They work with NRENs, academic libraries and the research community to support Open Science infrastructure, policy and advocacy for Open Science and capacity building. LIBSENSE hosts a preprint platform and data hub, [Baobab](#).

Lever 6: Collective action, influence, and science diplomacy

No single funder or government can shift global publication norms alone. Collective action through Open Science coalitions, multilateral agreements, and science diplomacy amplifies individual influence and creates the shared incentive frameworks needed for preprints to thrive internationally. Policymakers and research funders should centre these efforts around the two major enabling agendas: Open Science (including Open Access) and research assessment reform.

A theory of change for how science diplomacy can support research publishing reform highlights the importance of elevating the issue on the international policy agenda and convening and coordination through global science networks (e.g., International Science Council – see spotlight below) and multilateral spaces (e.g., United Nations and G20) (Gulliver et al., 2024). Advancing these agendas can also be achieved through bilateral and multilateral research cooperation agreements with commitments to shared principles of Open Science including recognition of diverse outputs such as preprints. A shared incentive framework that recognises preprints is vital for joint research funding calls.

It is important that existing coalitions and reform efforts on Open Access recognise and support preprint sharing as a viable and equitable Open Access route. Research funders and STI policymakers should use their influence in Open Access reform efforts to ensure preprints are part of the solution.

Beyond formal coalitions, funders and policymakers can drive change through bilateral dialogue: encouraging research institutions to reform research assessment and academic incentives to reward open and early sharing of research, and engaging publishers who support community-owned preprint infrastructure as the first stage of the publishing workflow.

Spotlight: ISC Forum on Publishing and Research Assessment

The International Science Council (ISC) has long been a champion of research publishing reform. Recognising the interaction of publishing with research assessment in 2025 ISC launched the Forum on Publishing and Research Assessment. This forum aims to bring these two reform communities together to create concrete plans for coordinated action – supporting science as a global public good. This forum is an ideal space to advance preprint sharing as an equitable and open research publishing solution and ensure the necessary shifts in recognition of preprints in research assessment.

Spotlight: Action Plan for International Cooperation in Open Science

During South Africa's G20 presidency the African Union, Brazil, China and South Africa developed an Action Plan for International Cooperation in Open Science. This plan has the following objectives:

1. Advance global governance in Open Science in support of UNESCO and multilateral partnerships
2. Deepen global cooperation on the sharing of Open Science data
3. Develop and share research infrastructures and resources
4. Promote open circulation of world-class scientific journals
5. Enhance public understanding of and engagement with Open Science
6. Strengthen capacity-building in developing countries

Objective four specifically references promoting 'new formats such as preprints to close the scientific-information divide among countries and regions'.

Policy pointers for funders and policymakers

Lever	Policy Pointer	Policy makers	Research funders
Lever 1: National STI policies and Open Science commitments	Develop enabling national STI policies and Open Science strategies. These provide a national framework to signal prioritisation of Open Science to other public and private stakeholders. Preprint sharing is supported by commitments to affordable and equitable Open Access publication, transparent peer review, and recognition of diverse research outputs in research assessment.	✓	
	Support policy prioritisation by developing strong rationale for Open Science and preprints. Consider the arguments that will gain traction amongst different stakeholders e.g., the connection between preprints and scientific transparency and public access; the benefits of rapid access and reuse to speed up the scientific process; equity and levelling the playing field for researchers; the financial imperative for a more affordable research publishing system.	✓	✓
Lever 2: Preprint policies	Develop a standalone preprint policy or explicit reference to preprints within Open Access policies. Research funder support for preprints via a standalone policy or within their Open Access policies signals expectations around research dissemination and enhances legitimacy amongst other research stakeholders. Making it clear that preprints can be a route to Open Access compliance signals support for early sharing.		✓
	Communicate the benefits of preprints and how to share them within policy socialisation. Training and capacity strengthening should cover the benefits of preprints and technical guidance on how to share preprints, licensing and integration with publishing workflows.		✓

Lever	Policy Pointer	Policy makers	Research funders
Lever 3: Research assessment policies and frameworks	Recognise preprints in research assessment. Clear communication on the inclusion of preprints within research evaluation at all stages from grant application to grant review. A research funders' recognition of preprints needs to be visible and well communicated as otherwise researchers will assume standard requirements e.g., peer-reviewed articles.		✓
	Train and support review committees to understand importance of preprints. The role of preprints and their recognition in research assessment should be communicated with reviewers to avoid the perpetuation of biases towards prestige publication.		✓
	Advocate for national commitments to diverse research outputs. Where national regulations shape academic incentives, advocate for policy change in line with research assessment reform, recognising diverse outputs and the quality of research over publication venue. This can help drive institutional reform to research incentives to recognise preprints.	✓	
Lever 4: Awareness and capacity strengthening	Prioritise Open Science in national STI education frameworks. Signal the need for preprint literacy to institutions and partners providing training and skills development to students and researchers.	✓	
	Invest in training and support on preprint sharing. Support can be embedded within existing grantee support, researcher development or Open Science initiatives.		✓
	Provide grant or in-kind support for existing capacity strengthening and training initiatives. This helps build awareness across the research community and supports the development of resources and tools targeted at different stakeholders.		✓

Lever	Policy Pointer	Policy makers	Research funders
Lever 5: Support for preprint infrastructure	Position Open Science infrastructure as a foundational STI investment. Open infrastructure is understood as a public good that can unlock research and innovation. This should include preprint servers and related tools and services.	✓	
	Invest in community-led preprint and preprint peer review infrastructure. Investment can be guided by existing mechanisms or through assessment of the platforms and services that sustain Open Science within a funder's community of grantees.		✓
	Invest in pilots and innovations that support preprint sharing. Examples included funding mechanisms for community-led models, innovative approaches to preprint review including AI enabled approaches, journal overlay services, and preprint curation.		✓
Lever 6: Collective action, influence and science diplomacy	Join and support coalitions advancing shared global commitments and action on Open Science and research assessment reform. Ensure these coalitions recognise preprints as a viable Open Access route and prioritise recognition of diverse research outputs including preprints.	✓	
	Prioritise Open Science principles within scientific cooperation with other countries and institutions. Ensure collaboration agreements and joint calls are built upon a shared understanding of Open Science benefits and the importance of early sharing of evidence via preprints.		✓
	Influence research institution policies. This helps align academic incentives through recognition of preprints for hiring, career progression and degree awards through dialogue, cooperation and funding decisions.		✓
	Drive dialogue and influence with the research publishing sector. Build coalitions and partnerships with publishers and journals who support community-owned preprint servers as the first stage of the publishing workflow.	✓	✓

Annex: Approach to policy paper development

The contents of this policy paper were synthesised from a desk review of existing evidence and expert interviews with stakeholders in the preprint advocacy, policy and review space.

Desk review: we reviewed existing evidence and guidance on preprint sharing with a focus on ascertaining identified solutions or actions that could be driven by research funding agencies of science, technology and innovation policymakers. See References for list of articles and texts reviewed.

Expert interviews: we conducted seven 30-minute semi-structured interviews with experts in the preprint space this included: science policymakers, academic advocates, hosts of preprint infrastructure including servers and peer review platforms and open science advocacy organisations see [Table 4](#). below for a list of people we spoke with. The interviews explored:

- Barriers to sharing preprints amongst researchers and at what level those barriers sit e.g., research culture, institutional policy, publisher policy.
- The benefits of preprints and how to persuade research funders to invest and support them.
- The role of research funder Open Access policies in supporting preprint sharing.
- Infrastructure requirements for preprint sharing becoming mainstream.
- Future of preprints as a form of research communication.

The evidence from the desk review and interviews was analysed to identify policy pointers directed at different stakeholders.

Limitations

- The premise of this work and the authors' starting point was that sharing preprints is a good thing for science. We acknowledge there are counter views to this, but our analysis of evidence and interviews was structured around identifying how to support the adoption of preprint sharing across the research ecosystem.
- The number of people we interviewed was limited and could have included representatives from a broader range of institutions and geographies. The scale and focus of these interviews may have limited the variety of perspectives shared with us and fed into the policy pointers we developed.
- We did not directly engage with the perspectives of researchers especially those in the Global South who face greater challenges with the current research publishing system. Our insights would be enhanced by incorporating diverse researcher perspectives.
- Our review was constrained by time and resources, we were not able to review all the existing evidence and extensive academic literature in this space.
- Preprints are one small part of reforming research publishing and promoting Open Science. The policy pointers need to be looked at alongside existing commitments and related agendas facing research funders and STI policymakers to ensure harmonisation.

Table 4. Expert interviewees

Name	Organisation	Region
Emmanuel Boakye	Africa Reproducibility Network	Africa
Katie Corker	ASAPbio	North America
Lamis Yahia Mohamed Elkheir	Africa Reproducibility Network	Africa
Monica Granados	Creative Commons	North America
Jo Havemann	Access 2 Perspectives	Europe
Christopher Marcum	Former US Government Advisor	North America
Carolina Tanigushi	SciELO	South America

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